

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Perceived organizational support, work engagement, and employee well-Being

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Abstract

This study aims to analyze and explain the relationship between perceived organizational support, work engagement, and employee well-being. This research was conducted at Toya Devasya. The population in this study is 128 people. The number of samples used were all Toya Devasya employees, 128 employees, using the total sampling method. Data collection was obtained through questionnaires and interviews. The analysis technique used is descriptive statistical analysis and inferential statistical analysis. Data were analyzed using SEM (Structural Equation Modeling) with Partial Least Square (PLS) approach. The results showed that perceived organizational support had a positive and significant effect on employee well-being and work engagement, work engagement had a positive and significant effect on employee well-being. Work engagement complementary partially mediates the effect of perceived organizational support on employee well-being. Companies need to pay attention to the implementation of perceived organizational support and work engagement in a comprehensive manner so that employee well-being can be implemented better.

Keywords: Perceived Organizational Support; Work Engagement; Employee Well-Being

1. Introduction

Rizky & Sadida (2019) say that employee well-being is a subjective state that describes an employee's self at work which can be influenced by various things at work. Employee well-being can be defined in line with the hedonic perspective of happiness built on life satisfaction (Ariza et al., 2019). Employee well-being is a personal description that describes happiness, a balance between positive emotions, negative emotions, and global evaluations and is also the whole of a person's working life (Wright & Cropanzano, 2000). employee well-being is the overall quality of the way an employee experiences work and various functions at work (Marin & Bonavia, 2021) so that it becomes very basic in work (Ogbonnaya et al., 2018). One of the factors that can affect employee well-being is work engagement (Uliani, 2020). Work engagement is an attitude that describes individuals as fully involved with their work, both emotionally and physically by showing passionate, dedicated, and appreciative behaviour in carrying out work (Mufarrikhah, 2020). According to Wingerden et al., (2018) work engagement can occur when employees proactively seek challenges, engage experiences and motivate by producing effective problem solving in solving problems. produce an effective problem solving in completing work.

Bakker et al., (2019) explained that work engagement has an important role in efforts to achieve organizational success because work engagement includes aspects that include positive emotions, full involvement in work. A number of studies (Fadila & Uliani, 2020: Bakker et al., 2018), state that work engagement has a positive and significant effect on employee well-being. According to Iswanto & Agustina (2016), organizations that have employees with good work engagement will get many benefits and make the organization more advanced and developed.

The results of the preliminary study also indicate that employees feel less enthusiastic and less excited about completing work. This makes the work done feel less meaningful to employees. Enthusiasm at work is also felt to have decreased

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due to unstable working conditions due to the Covid 19 pandemic. In addition, due to the prolonged pandemic, working conditions at a number of tourism facilities and supports have decreased in performance. In fact, a number of employees were given a division of work shifts up to termination of employment. This condition makes Toya Devasya employees experience shock because of the uncertainty of work. Ogbonnaya et al. (2018) state that various problems faced by employees in the workplace can be overcome by the presence of the organization to provide support. Organizational support for employees is termed perceived organizational support (POS) which can cause employees to feel engaged with work and feel more well-being.

Pangestusi (2018) states that POS is an employee's belief that the organization cares and values their contribution to the success of the organization. Malik & Noreen (2015) say POS is a concept that has been used to assess an organization's handling of employees which describes how much the organization values and supports employees to perform job roles effectively. Meanwhile, Pangestusi (2018) states that perceived POS is the level to which employees believe the organization values their contributions and cares about their welfare. Woerkom et al. (2016) state that POS is defined as the extent to which employees feel actively supported by the organization to use their unique strengths at work.

Research by Mufarrihah et al. (2020) states that POS has a positive and significant effect on work engagement. This can be interpreted that the higher the POS, the more employee work engagement will increase. The perceptions that employees have can determine their full involvement in the work they are doing, whether it is a positive perception or a negative perception. In addition, Sitanggang (2018) stated that there is a significant influence between POS with work engagement and employee well-being (Caesens et al. 2016). The results of research by Rahmi et al. (2021) also stated that POS has a positive effect on work engagement where employees have a positive view that the organization shows concern as part of the organization, cares about the effort shown at work, and the organization appreciates the efforts of each of its members in contributing to the running of the wheels of the organization.

High POS provides an indication that help will be received by employees when needed, making employees anticipate the future with more confidence and thus resulting in higher subjective well-being (Eisenberger and Stinglhamber, 2011). Kurtessis et al. (2017) stated that POS is important to support organizational performance outcomes to improve employee well-being. Ogbonnaya et al. (2018) stated that POS can improve employee well-being and increase work engagement with the organization. POS is also seen to strengthen work engagement and make employees able to work better to improve services.

2. Literature review and hypothesis development

Perceived organizational support (POS) can strengthen employee engagement which results in employees being able to work well and thus improve services. High POS indicates that help will be received by employees when needed, making employees anticipate the future with more confidence and thus resulting in higher subjective well-being (Eisenberger and Stinglhamber, 2011).

Research by Caesens et al. (2016) states that POS has a positive and significant effect on employee well-being. Kurtessis et al. (2017) shows that POS is important to support organisational performance outcomes so that it can improve employee well-being. Ogbonnaya et al. (2018) state that POS is able to improve employee well-being and increase employee attachment to the organisation. In addition, research conducted by Watto et al. (2018) also stated that POS has a positive effect on employee well-being. Setyoko & Kurniasih (2022) also found in their research that POS has a positive and significant effect on employee well-being. Anantha & Pratiwi (2022) also found that POS has a positive and significant effect on employee well-being. This result is in line with research (Wong, 2018) that found POS has a positive and

- H1: Perceived organizational support has a positive and significant effect on employee well-being.

Perceived organizational support is defined as the extent to which employees feel actively supported by their organisation to use their unique strengths at work (Woerkom et al., 2016). Research by Mufarrihah et al. (2020) states that POS has a positive and significant effect on work engagement. This can be interpreted that the higher the perceived organizational support, the more employee work engagement will increase. In addition, Sitanggang's research (2018) states that there is a positive and significant influence between POS and work engagement.

The results of research from Rahmi et al. (2021) also states that POS has a positive effect on work engagement, while research conducted by Hardianto & Ratna (2022) also states that there is a positive and significant influence between POS and work engagement, in the research of Utari et al. (2021) also stated that POS has a positive and significant effect

on work engagement. Research by Canboy et al. (2021) also found that perceived organizational support is positively related to work engagement, besides that, Tan et al. (2020) stated that perceived organizational support is positively related to work engagement.

- H2: Perceived organizational support has a positive and significant effect on work engagement.

Research conducted by Fadila & Uliani (2020) states that work engagement has a positive and significant effect on employee well-being, besides that Bakker et al., (2018), also found that work engagement has a positive and significant effect on employee well-being. Research conducted by Wajong et al. (2019) found that work engagement has a positive and significant effect on employee well-being, besides that research conducted by Radic et al. (2020) also found that there is a positive influence between work engagement on employee well-being.

- H3: Work engagement has a positive and significant effect on employee well-being

Specifically, work engagement is a state of well-being and affective commitment and motivation to work (Schaufeli & Bakker, 2004). Woerkom et al. (2016) state perceived organizational support is defined as the extent to which employees feel actively supported by their organization to use their unique strengths at work (Woerkom et al., 2016). The results of research from Rahmi et al. (2021) also stated that POS has a positive effect on work engagement, while research conducted by Fadila & Uliani (2020) stated that work engagement has a positive and significant effect on employee well-being. Man & Hadi (2013) state that there is a positive relationship between POS and work engagement.

- H4: Work engagement mediates the effect of perceived organizational support on employee well-being.

3. Methods

The population in this study were all 128 employees of Toya Devasya. The sample determined was all 128 Toya Devasya employees. The sampling technique in this study was total sampling (saturated sample). Total sampling is sampling, where the sample taken is the same as the total population. The data analysis technique used in this research is using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) or variance-based structural equation models or component-based SEM called Partial Least Square (PLS). SEM PLS analysis in the study was carried out with the Smart PLS 3.0 software application.

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Internal Consistency Reliability

The criteria for internal consistency reliability are measured using Cronbach's alpha value. The composite reliability value ranges from 0 to 1, with the criteria for a good and acceptable value for research is greater than 0.60 (>0.60) (Hair et al., 2017: 126). The internal consistency reliability value can be seen in Table 1 below:

Table 1 Internal Consistency Reliability

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability
Employee Well-being	0.923	0.931
Perceived Organizational Support	0.705	0.857
Work Engagement	0.912	0.914

Primary Data, 2023

The results of SEM PLS analysis show that each Cronbach's Alpha of the Employee Well-being variable is 0.923; the Perceived Organizational Support variable is 0.705; and the Work Engagement variable is 0.912 greater than 0.60, so the research instrument can be said to meet the requirements of composite reliability.

4.2. Convergent Validity

The convergent validity test is used to measure the correlation between constructs in the research model (Hair et al., 2017: 127). The research variable construct will be declared valid if it has an outer loading value greater than 0.70

(>0.70). The following are the results of convergent validity testing of employee well-being indicators, perceived organizational support and work engagement in Table 2.

Table 2 Outer Model

Variable	Dimension	Indicator	Outer Model	Result
Perceived Organizational Support	Valuing contribution	X1	0.716	Valid
	Appreciating extra effort	X2	0.716	Valid
	Attentive to grievances	X3	0.762	Valid
	Caring about welfare	X4	0.706	Valid
	Informing when not doing a good job	X5	0.817	Valid
	Cares about job satisfaction	X6	0.859	Valid
	General job satisfaction	X7	0.772	Valid
	Gives great attention to work	X8	0.876	Valid
Work Engagement		Y1.1.1	0.79	Valid
	Vigor	Y1.1.2	0.793	Valid
		Y1.1.3	0.806	Valid
		Y1.2.1	0.740	Valid
	Dedication	Y1.2.2	0.714	Valid
		Y1.2.3	0.740	Valid
		Y1.2.4	0.788	Valid
		Y1.3.1	0.811	Valid
	Absorption	Y1.3.2	0.751	Valid
		Y1.3.3	0.731	Valid
Employee Well-being	Career	Y2.1.1	0.823	Valid
		Y2.1.2	0.769	Valid
	Social	Y2.2.1	0.834	Valid
		Y2.2.2	0.822	Valid
	Financial	Y2.3.1	0.847	Valid
		Y2.3.2	0.806	Valid
	Physical	Y2.4.1	0.729	Valid
		Y2.4.2	0.721	Valid
	Community	Y2.5.1	0.723	Valid
		Y2.5.2	0.702	Valid

Primary Data, 2023

Based on Table 3, it shows that all indicators of the dimensions of the employee well-being variable, perceived organizational support and work engagement have an outer loading value of more than 0.70, so it can be concluded that all indicators are valid.

4.3. Discriminant Validity

Discriminant validity test is carried out by measuring indicators based on cross loading with latent variables. The instrument is declared valid if the cross loading value of each indicator on the variable concerned has a value greater than the correlation on other latent variables. The following are the results of discriminant validity testing in Table 5.7 below

Table 3 Cross Loading

	Perceived OrganizationalSupport	Work Engagement	Employee Well-being
X1	0.716	0.416	0.413
X2	0.716	0.514	0.512
X3	0.762	0.514	0.604
X4	0.706	0.609	0.601
X5	0.817	0.617	0.634
X6	0.859	0.651	0.683
X7	0.772	0.642	0.565
X8	0.876	0.727	0.707
Y1.1.1	0.487	0.790	0.655
Y1.1.2	0.566	0.793	0.688
Y1.1.3	0.654	0.806	0.700
Y1.2.1	0.537	0.740	0.639
Y1.2.2	0.489	0.714	0.657
Y1.2.3	0.482	0.740	0.670
Y1.2.4	0.548	0.788	0.715
Y1.3.1	0.500	0.811	0.710
Y1.3.2	0.736	0.751	0.549
Y1.3.3	0.843	0.731	0.697
Y2.1.1	0.634	0.777	0.823
Y2.1.2	0.517	0.720	0.769
Y2.2.1	0.594	0.770	0.834
Y2.2.2	0.588	0.789	0.822
Y2.3.1	0.674	0.814	0.847
Y2.3.2	0.595	0.733	0.806
Y2.4.1	0.472	0.464	0.729
Y2.4.2	0.661	0.599	0.721
Y2.5.1	0.622	0.596	0.723
Y2.5.2	0.676	0.532	0.702

Primary Data, 2023

Based on Table 3, it shows that the results of all latent variable correlation discriminant validity items in each variable are greater than 0.5 and have a higher value than other latent variables. Thus, it can be concluded that all indicators have met the discriminant validity requirements.

4.4. Evaluation of the Structural Model (Inner Model)

4.4.1. R-Square (R²)

The calculation of the R-Square (R²) value aims to see the magnitude of the correlation value of the endogenous variables resulting from the PLS estimate on each path (Hair et al., 2017: 213). The R-square (R²) value ranges from 0 to 1, the higher the R-square value indicates the better the research structural model. The results of R² can be seen in Table 4 below:

Table 4 R-Square Test Results (R²)

Variable	R-Square (R ²)
Employee Well-being	0.812
Work Engagement	0.628

Primary Data, 2023

In the results of SEM PLS analysis, each R Square of the Employee Well-being (Y2) variable is 0.812 and the Work Engagement (Y1) variable is 0.628.

4.4.2. Square predictive relevance

The Q-Square predictive relevance value for structural models is used to measure the value of observations generated by the model and model parameter estimates. The Q-square (Q²) value > 0 indicates the model has predictive relevance, otherwise if the Q² value ≤ 0 indicates the model lacks predictive relevance (Hair et al., 2017: 222).

$$Q^2 = 1 - (1 - R^2) (1 - R^2)$$

$$Q^2 = 1 - (1 - 0,812) (1 - 0,628)$$

$$Q^2 = 1 - (0,188) (0,372)$$

$$Q^2 = 1 - 0,0699 = 0,9301$$

The results above show a predictive relevance value of 0.9301. This value is greater than 0, so it can be interpreted that 93.01 per cent of the variation in the EWB variable is explained by the variables used in the model. The remaining 6.99 per cent is explained by other factors outside the model. With these results, it is concluded that this model has relevant predictive value.

4.5. Hypothesis Testing

4.5.1. Direct effect

Table 5 Direct Effect

Pengaruh Langsung	Path Coefficient	T Statistics	P Value	Keterangan
Perceived Organizational Support (X) -> Employee Well-being (Y2)	0.187	2.051	0.034	Valid
Perceived Organizational Support (X) -> Work Engagement (Y1)	0.794	21.447	0.000	Valid
Work Engagement (Y1) -> Employee Well-being (Y2)	0.747	8.544	0.000	Valid

Primary Data, 2023

4.5.2. Perceived Organizational Support (X) on Employee Well-being (Y2)

Based on the results of the SEM PLS bootstrapping analysis, the results of the effect of Perceived Organizational Support on Employee Well-being have a P value of 0.034 < 0.05. This means that the test results are significant, in other words

H1 in this study is accepted, namely Perceived Organizational Support has a positive and significant effect on Employee Well-being.

4.5.3. Perceived Organizational Support (X) on Work Engagement (Y1)

Based on the results of the SEM PLS bootstrapping analysis, the results of the effect of Perceived Organizational Support on Work Engagement have a P value of 0.000 < 0.05. This means that the test results are significant, in other words, H2 in this study is accepted, namely Perceived Organizational Support has a positive and significant effect on Work Engagement.

4.5.4. Work Engagement (Y1) on Employee Well-being (Y2)

Based on the results of SEM PLS bootstrapping analysis, the results of the effect of Work Engagement on Employee Well-being have a P value of 0.000 < 0.05. This means that the test results are significant, in other words H3 in this study is accepted, namely Work Engagement has a positive and significant effect on Employee Well-being.

4.5.5. Indirect Effect

Table 6 Indirect Effect

Variable	Path Coefficients	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T-Statistics	P-Value	Result
Perceived Organizational Support -> Work Engagement -> Employee Well-Being	0.593	0.074	8.049	0.000	Valid

Primary Data, 2023

Based on the results of the study, it is found that the influence of all variables, namely perceived organizational support → work engagement has a significant positive effect, work engagement → employee well-being has a significant positive effect and perceived organizational support → employee well-being has a significant positive effect. So it can be concluded that the type of mediation obtained is complementary partial mediation.

5. Conclusion

Perceived organizational support has a positive and significant effect on employee well-being, perceived organizational support has a positive and significant effect on work engagement, work engagement has a positive and insignificant effect on employee well-being, and work engagement is able to mediate the effect of perceived organizational support on employee well-being. Based on these findings, the results of this study are able to enrich the development of human resource management science, especially related to employee well-being related to employee well-being and support the results of other related empirical studies regarding the analysis of the influence of perceived organizational support, work engagement, and employee well-being.

The results of the study can be used practically by management as input and consideration regarding policy making to increase employee well-being at Toya Devasya. The policies owned by Toya Devasya should be able to consider the balance between perceived organizational support, work engagement, and employee well-being. Toya Devasya can socialise the support that the company will provide to employees so that employees feel the relationship so that later it can help improve their well-being. In addition, to improve the welfare of employees, companies also need to increase employee work engagement so that employees can work wholeheartedly and be able to achieve company goals.

Research Limitations

- The scope of the research was only conducted on Toya Devasya employees, so the results of this study can have differences if the research is conducted on other companies that are also engaged in tourism.
- This study examines the mediating role of OCB in analyzing the effect of perceived organizational support, work engagement, and employee well-being. There are many other variables that can be further tested related to employee well-being in Toya Devasya employees and other research that can be conducted and further explored on Toya Devasya employees.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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